

COALESCE

Co-creating the EU Competence Centre for
Science Communication

Deliverable 3.1

Co-designed virtual Competence Centre requirements specifications

Version: v1.0

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Deliverable Details

Due date 30th June 2024	Actual submission date 30th June 2024	Start date 1st Apr 2023	Duration 4 years
Work package concerned WP3	Concerned work package leader SFC	Concerned work package co-leader LUT	Dissemination level PU – public <i>must be available on the website</i>

Authors Joana Magalhães (SFC), Blanca Guasch (SFC), Rosa Arias (SFC), Abdul Abbasi (LUT), Annika Wolff (LUT), Antti Knutas (LUT)

Reviewers Jason Pridmore (EUR)

Revision history

Revision	Date	Author/ Contributor	Description
v1.0	31/05/2024	Joana Magalhães (SFC), Blanca Guasch (SFC)	First draft
v1.1	14/06/2024	Abdul Abbasi (LUT), Annika Wolff (LUT), Antti Knutas (LUT)	Second draft and first review
V1.2	02/07/2024	Joana Magalhães (SFC), Rosa Arias (SFC)	Final version
v1.3	08/07/2024	Jason Pridmore (EUR)	Final review and approval

HOW TO CITE THIS DELIVERABLE

Magalhães J, Guasch B, Arias R, Abbasi A, Wolff A, Knutas A. (2024). Co-designed virtual Competence Centre requirements specifications. Deliverable report (D3.1), COALESCE project (grant agreement No 101095230), funded by the European Union. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12088890

STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

DISCLAIMER

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

1 Introduction.....	4
1.1 About the COALESCE project.....	4
1.2 About the European Competence Centre for Science Communication.....	4
1.3 Stakeholders.....	5
2 Co-design and co-development methodological framework.....	7
2.1 General Methodology.....	7
2.2 Description of iterations and timeline.....	17
2.3 Description of platform releases.....	17
2.4 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).....	18
3 Co-design of CC requirements specifications (overall and 1st release).....	19
3.1 Methodology.....	19
3.1.1 Co-design sessions for needs and user requirements.....	20
3.1.2 Semi-structured interviews for needs and user requirements.....	27
3.1.3 Technical mapping for functional requirements.....	28
3.2 Results.....	29
3.2.1 Needs and requirements identified for platform and each tool.....	29
3.2.2 User requirements specifications 1.....	32
3.2.2.1 Virtual platform.....	32
3.2.2.2 Library of resources.....	33
3.2.2.3 Scicomm Academy.....	36
3.2.2.4 Impact & Self Assessment Tool.....	38
3.2.2.5 Misinformation Tool.....	38
3.2.2.6 Matchmaking Tool.....	39
3.2.2.7 Mobilisation in time of crisis.....	41
3.2.2.8 Space for joint events, ML, and networking.....	42
3.2.2.9 Other Tools or considerations.....	42
3.2.3 User requirements specifications 2 - for 1st release.....	43
3.2.4 General high level architecture of the platform.....	44
3.2.5 Functional requirements - virtual platform general.....	45
3.2.6 Functional requirements - for 1st release.....	46
3.2.7 Functional requirements - collaboration with ECS and other projects.....	50
4 Risks.....	51
5 Final Remarks.....	51
6 Acknowledgements.....	52
7 Project details.....	52
Appendix 1.....	53
Appendix 2.....	55

1 Introduction

1.1 About the COALESCE project

The [Coordinated Opportunities for Advanced Leadership and Engagement in Science Communication in Europe](#) (COALESCE) project is funded by the European Commission (EC) to establish the European Science Communication Competence Centre (henceforth “Competence Centre”), and an associated Science Communication Academy (“SciComm Academy”). The Competence Centre is based on a virtual platform, offering services, tools and resources through a network of physical national and regional (N&R) hubs. The Competence Centre will initially be developed through [consolidation of learning from projects](#) funded through the “Science with and for Society” (SwafS-19) programme as part of Horizon 2020, namely TRESKA, NEWSERA, PARCOS, GlobalScape, QUEST, ENJOI, CONCISE and RETHINK. The role of the Competence Centre is to further develop and mainstream science communication knowledge and to foster connections between science and society.

The Competence Centre will be reinforced by the External Stakeholder Panel (ESP), which will be made up of topic networks; national, international and regional networks of science communication or related areas; professional networks; university alliances; and a network of N&R hubs. These will be established in EU countries as well as the UK and Ukraine. More than 5000 people who were involved in previously funded SwafS-19 projects will be invited to establish the COALESCE communities of knowledge and practice (CoP).

1.2 About the European Competence Centre for Science Communication

The [Competence Centre virtual platform](#) will be built during the project duration of four years (April 2023 – March 2027), and is expected to become fully operational and sustainable by the end of the project. Its main goal will be to support recognition and the professionalisation of scicomm, as well as offer knowledge, expertise, advice, resources, and tools, to all research and innovation actors, including scicomm professionals, journalists and quadruple helix (4H) stakeholders (researchers, industry, policymakers, citizens).

The co-development of the Competence Centre virtual platform, guidelines, tools, services and recommendations will feed directly from continuous knowledge consolidation and different participatory and co-creation processes to be undertaken with members from the COALESCE ESP, N&R Hubs and CoP, through a series of activities with relevant stakeholders from diverse sectors involved in science communication.

A co-design-co-development methodological framework has been developed in order to ensure the incorporation of end-user-producer needs and expectations, to offer a basket of interactive services and activities with market value, and also build capacity, promote mutual learning and networking. The Competence Centre activities will continue beyond the project

lifetime through its sustainability model, supported through face to face activities run by the N&R hubs network.

The Competence Centre virtual platform will be creating a marketplace resulting from the application of the [SciComm Innovation Cycle](#), and all content made available through the platform will be analysed under quality criteria for science communication prior to publication. The virtual platform will offer specific interactive tools, such as a matchmaking tool, a pedagogical toolkit and a scicomm impact self-evaluation tool. It will include dedicated spaces for the SciComm Academy, a library of resources and the [ENJOI Observatory](#), specifically addressing journalism. And finally it will also have interactive capabilities and spaces to joint discussions to allow mutual learning, to plan and organise joint events and networking.

1.3 Stakeholders

The COALESCE project and Competence Centre main stakeholders as early defined are all the scicomm actors from the European Research Area.

We can divide these in the following:

Scicomm professionals: Professionals who work in scicomm in both public and private companies, institutions, museums and science centres have difficulties getting their messages across all audiences, and there are segments of society who remain underserved and untouched

Informal or non-traditional scicommers: Youtubers, Igers, TikTokers, influencers, using various social media channels for their communication practices are a particularly challenging group to reach as they are not typically part of established networks and may not consider themselves as 'scicommers'

Science and non science journalists: Media professionals have uneven training and particular up to date scientific breakthroughs or related to critical situations and access to a variety of reliable expert sources affects specially the generalist journalist

Researchers: Scientists from all disciplines, not just academics, involved in scicomm practices

Government agencies, public authorities and RPFs: Local, regional, and national decision makers and funding bodies working on R&I or sectoral policies. Civic servants, intermediaries, analysts, consultants

Citizens: Citizens interested in scicomm and groups at risk of social exclusion, women and girls

Third sector, NGOs, grassroots communities: Organisations doing scicomm or interested in it, including independent art-related researchers and practitioners

Industry, businesses and innovation hubs scicomm professionals: Scicomm professionals and Corporate Social Responsibility Units in medium to large enterprises, specially in the selected critical topics; start-ups, incubators, accelerators; digital innovation hubs; living labs

2 Co-design and co-development methodological framework

2.1 General Methodology

In order to define the platform co-design and co-development (CDD) methodological framework to be undertaken within the COALESCE project, a literature review, an internal brainstorm session and periodic mutual learnings meetings were conducted. The main goal was to understand processes, commonalities, lessons learnt and points of improvement, and build upon previously tested and validated methodologies under the [COS4CLOUD](#)¹, [ECS](#)² and [PARCOS](#)³ EU-H2020 funded projects. Furthermore, aspects such as interoperability and complementarity of services/tools/resources are being considered and explored with ongoing collaborations amongst the COALESCE, ECS, [PATTERN](#), [REINFORCING](#) and [Skills4EOSC](#) projects.

This methodological framework is intended to provide a live plan for the strategy, requirements and tasks to be undertaken by the CDD core group, composed of Science for Change (SFC) and Lappeenranta-Lahti University of Technology (LUT) team members, in close collaboration with COALESCE partners, especially those responsible for the co-creation of any tool/resource/service (or simply “product”) to be incorporated in the platform (for simplification and for the onset of this document will be referred to as “content providers”). As such, the processes for the co-creation of products, co-design of user requirements and co-development within the platform will need a combined team effort and strong collaboration under short time periods and considering multiple interlinkages between the different products so that they allow optimal user experience, ensure the maximum impact and exploitability of the COALESCE outputs.

It will be defined and updated by the CDD core group and will inform the co-design and co-development activities undertaken under the aegis of the project, allowing for flexibility in response to changing needs and challenges detected, including those beyond the period funded by the EC.

The methodological framework will consist of multiple phases divided into – pre-development, development and deployment (**Figure 1**). It should allow an efficient collaboration between the co-design of user requirements, the co-creation of content and an agile co-development, in order to constantly and iteratively feed into input work streams. The application of co-design methodologies in early stages of the development process of

¹ Guasch, B., Amo, A., Hernández, M., Arias, R., Liñán, S., Piera, J., Justamante, Á., Fabó, C., & Soacha, K. (2022). Co-design as a service: Methodological guide. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472450>

² Sanz, F., Gold, M., & Mazzone, M. (2019). D2.3: Platform Functionality Requirements & Specification Report (Version Final Submitted draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3612808>

³Victoria P. (2020). Platform Requirements, deliverable 6.1 of the Horizon 2020 project ParCos, EC grant agreement no 872500, Lappeenranta, Finland.

the IT services and resources, as core modules of the virtual CC, such as for the obtainment of user requirements specifications, ensures that the tools and products will provide value, usability and an attractive user experience, but also that we guarantee maximum compliance from the beginning, which ultimately can benefit and optimise the full development process. Whilst participatory methodologies with a producer-user-centred approach will be considered as *gold standard*, other internal/external consultation processes will be taken into account to facilitate operations, when deemed appropriate and necessary.

Figure 1. EU Competence Centre for Scicomm platform co-design and co-development methodological process.

Hereby we describe in more detail each of the three phases, including main tasks, supporting documentation and tools to be used, partners involved and roles and outputs:

Phase 1: pre-development (ideation, framing the needs, co-design of user requirements, define user requirements specifications, conversion to functional requirements specifications)

a) Brainstorming

The CDD process for each tool will start with a meeting with the different content providers to discuss and brainstorm the ideas for the product to be developed and incorporated in the virtual platform. We will define the main goal, expected output, potential stakeholders and end users, status update of content creation phase, main contacts and a timeline. The CDD team then presents the methodological framework for discussion on specific aspects. Minutes and all relevant information will be registered in a “user requirement specifications” (URS) document (see Appendix 1),

created for each of the tools, which will be updated in the different sub-phases of the pre-development process.

- b) Defining, implementing and analysing the co-design process for user requirements

Thereafter, a co-design session, and/or other methodologies (such as semi-structured interviews, surveys, etc), will be proposed to understand the needs and expectations of stakeholders, their impressions of the proposed product and finally to obtain user requirements. This will be based on a pre-defined concept note that includes co-design session methodology⁴, number and typology of participants to be recruited, an annotated basis to create an infographic of the tool and user-expected-interaction in the platform and an online collaborative board template (using Miro software). The co-design methodology process, concept note and associated documentation have been created to be easily adapted in both individual and multiple and interconnected product(s) contexts. In principle, two co-design sessions are planned for each of the products, however, and as explained, this number can vary according to the final decision and product interconnections.

Co-design sessions will be facilitated by SFC, with the support of the content providers, with the duration of 2,5h, to be set online (via Zoom or other similar), although face to face sessions could be considered if coincident with COALESCE events or any relevant scicomm community events. Pre-identified members of CoPs, N&R hubs and ESPs will be invited as participants (up to 30 people per session). After each session, SFC will create a co-design digest report that will include: user's input according to the specific role by stakeholder type, its purpose and finally relevance for the project itself. These will feed the URS document (Appendix), and shared both to the content provider as well as LUT for further discussion.

Moreover, other more general and overarching requirements can be set by the project partners, such as measuring associated key performance indicators (KPIs) (see table 6) such as number of downloads, visits, active users, etc.

- c) Mapping and validating functional requirements

Thereafter, URS will be evaluated for technical requirements mapping, considering feasibility and priority, and converted into *functional requirements* (FR) for providing a technical solution by LUT and validated by SFC and content providers. This will constitute the basis for the *minimum viable product* (MVP) leading to the planned releases of the platform, as explained in section 2.2.

In **table 1**, a description of the sub-tasks, roles and responsibilities, material needed and expected outputs is included.

⁴ Guasch, B., Amo, A., Hernández, M., Arias, R., Liñán, S., Piera, J., Justamante, Á., Fabó, C., & Soacha, K. (2022). Co-design as a service: Methodological guide. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472450>

Table 1. Sub-tasks, roles and responsibilities, material needed, expected outputs

Sub-tasks	Roles & responsibilities	Material needed	Expected outputs
Brainstorming	<p>1) CDD (SFC and LUT): organise meeting and confirm information requested by content provider; explain the process and set a timeline and activities</p> <p>2) Content provider (Partners): may request meeting when needed; update on content status and information needed to start the process</p>	User requirement specification document; presentation of the process; relevant information on content and state of the art	agreement on workflow, roles and responsibilities, timeline
Defining, implementing and analysing the co-design process for user requirements	<p>1) SFC – coordinator co-design activity, participant recruiter, activity facilitator, collection of informed consents; analysing activity and creating report</p> <p>2) Content provider – support definition of activity, create infographic; support recruitment and facilitation of activity</p> <p>3) Data manager (EUR) – defining informed consents – and archiving</p> <p>4) CoP coordination (VIU) – facilitate participants contacts</p> <p>5) Development leader (LUT): support activity definition and facilitation, review URS</p>	concept note; online collaborative board, infographic of product; participants informed consents;	user requirements specifications (URS)
Mapping and validating functional requirements	<p>1) Business Analyst (LUT and SFC): Create detailed requirement documents with the help of user stories, use cases, and functional specification</p> <p>2) SFC. Analyse and prioritise requirements based on business value, feasibility, and impact. Communicate with Content providers to ensure all requirements are understood and agreed upon.</p> <p>3) Product Owner (LUT and SFC): Define the product vision, scope, and goals to guide the development process. Maintain and prioritise the product backlog, ensuring it reflects current</p>	user requirements specifications (URS)	functional requirements (FR) specifications;

	<p>needs and requirements. Create and refine user stories that capture functional requirements from an end-user perspective.</p> <p>4) System Architect (LUT): Assess the feasibility of functional requirements in terms of system architecture and design. Translate functional requirements into technical specifications and system designs.</p>		
--	--	--	--

Phase 2: development (from design, communication, development, quality assurance and validation)

The development process will follow an agile methodology that focuses on incremental improvement through a series of iterative development cycles. An agile process is appropriate for COALESCE as many tools are still being conceived and developed and it is not possible to capture all project requirements up front as would be required in a waterfall approach. LUT are responsible for managing the agile development process. To this end, LUT holds weekly stand ups to discuss progress and identify blockers. Progress is tracked using a Kanban board. In the early stages of development, the Drupal environment was selected as the most appropriate for implementing the platform, based on the initial requirements gathered through co-creation sessions. The process for implementing the platform is to first understand the requirements for the parts of the platform to be implemented, then develop LoFi prototypes that reflect the requirements, validate them through end-user testing and, once validated, implement them in Drupal. Thereafter a HiFi prototype is created to define the visual design which will also be validated. The end-user testing in the initial stages will be carried out within the consortium as the product owners act as end-users, but in later stages as the tools implemented within the platform become more complex, the end-user base will be extended to end-users outside the consortium.

In **table 2**, a description of the sub-tasks, roles and responsibilities, material needed and expected outputs is included.

Table 2. Sub-tasks, roles and responsibilities, material needed, expected outputs

Sub-tasks	Roles & responsibilities	Material needed	Expected outputs
Prototyping and validating the frontend grey structure	1) UX/UI Designer (LUT): Create wireframes that represent the grey structure of the frontend, focusing on layout, structure, and basic navigation without detailed	functional requirements (FR) specifications; prototyping tool;	Wireframes; prototypes;

	<p>design elements. Develop interactive prototypes to demonstrate the flow and functionality of the interface. Refine wireframes and prototypes based on feedback from stakeholders and users.</p> <p>2) Design Validator (SFC): Checking whether the layout and grey structure is meeting all the required functional features after communicating to relevant stakeholders.</p>		
<p>Designing and validating logo and required graphics plus content</p>	<p>1) Logo Designer (outsourced by LUT): Meet with clients to understand their vision, brand identity, target audience, and specific requirements for the logo.</p> <p>Analyse the brand's current visual identity, mission, values, and market positioning.</p> <p>Study the industry, competitors, and current design trends to ensure the logo is relevant and stands out in the market.</p> <p>Generate ideas and inspiration based on research, brainstorming, and creative thinking.</p> <p>Create initial sketches and drafts of logo concepts.</p> <p>Develop multiple logo concepts and variations for client review.</p> <p>Choose appropriate fonts, colours, and design elements that reflect the brand's identity, and are connected to the COALESCE project logo, including the distinctive "CC".</p> <p>Present logo concepts to the client, explaining the</p>	<p>Wireframes; visual content; logo;</p>	<p>logo; images; files; content;</p>

	<p>rationale behind each design. Gather feedback from the client and make necessary revisions to refine the logo design.</p> <p>2) Graphic Designer (FB) create visual elements that establish a relation with the visual narrative from the COALESCE project website</p> <p>LUT: Appropriate fonts, colours, and design elements that enhance the visual appeal and effectiveness of the design will be defined according to COALESCE visual branding guide.</p> <p>Arrange elements in a visually pleasing and functional layout that guides the viewer's attention effectively.</p> <p>3) Content Provider: Conduct thorough research on topics to ensure accurate and comprehensive information is presented.</p> <p>Write high-quality content for various formats, including, pdf and HTML, product descriptions, and more.</p> <p>4) CDD with Comm & Diss: Incorporate SEO best practices to enhance content visibility and improve search engine rankings, including the use of keywords, meta tags, and internal/external links.</p> <p>4) CDD (SFC): validate content, LoFi and HiFi</p>		
Finalising the look and feel	<p>1) UI/UX Expert (LUT): Study competitors' websites to understand industry standards and trends.</p> <p>Research current design trends and best practices within the industry.</p>	UI/UX requirements;	theme for frontend

	<p>Ensure the theme is compatible with the existing technology stack and platforms (e.g., CMS compatibility).</p> <p>Verify that the theme is fully responsive and works well on different devices and screen sizes.</p> <p>Ensure the theme performs consistently across various web browsers.</p> <p>2) Validation with SFC</p>		
Actual development	<p>1) Software Developer (LUT):</p> <p>Write clean, efficient, and maintainable code based on design specifications and requirements.</p> <p>Adhere to coding standards and guidelines, using appropriate tools and languages.</p> <p>Develop and execute unit tests to ensure code quality and functionality.</p> <p>Conduct integration tests to ensure different system components work together as expected.</p> <p>Identify, debug, and fix software defects and issues.</p> <p>Provide regular updates on project progress, challenges, and risks to project managers and stakeholders.</p> <p>Clarify requirements and specifications with stakeholders when necessary.</p>	<p>functional requirements (FR) specifications; wireframes; content; theme; graphics; associated files i.e. PDFs; development environment and tools;</p>	<p>developed web platform</p>

Phase 3: deployment (connected to a dissemination and exploitation strategy)

For the virtual platform deployment, SFC will set a domain and hosting for the virtual platform according to the defined needs, project strategy and any EC compliance security requirements. The infrastructure setup and configuration will be performed as described below. LUT and SFC will be in close collaboration in order to secure appropriate building, packaging, further testing and final deployment.

The CDD team will be in close collaboration with the Comm, Diss and Exploitation Team in order to define the best strategies to ensure higher visibility and reach to our target audiences (as already defined in the COALESCE Comm, Diss and Exploitation plan). This will be done by previous analysis of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) that include, the Competence Centre virtual platform itself and all its resources, the SciComm Academy and training courses. The exploitable results will include materials aimed at those communicating science, such as the library of resources, handbooks for effective science communication and strategies to address critical challenges, as well as materials relevant to actors engaged in the science communication policy and those who define the environment in which science communication takes place, such as universities and research funding bodies.

The dissemination and communication approaches will be aimed at maximising the visibility of exploitable results with intended audiences such that they gain maximum impact and relevance, and foster the exploitation of resources connected to the Competence Centre sustainability.

Finally, exploitation strategies to be defined under the COALESCE project business model will also be tested and further included as user requirements, feeding the CDD loop.

In **table 3**, a description of the sub-tasks, roles and responsibilities, material needed and expected outputs is included.

Table 3. Sub-tasks, roles and responsibilities, material needed, expected outputs

Sub-tasks	Roles & responsibilities	Material needed	Expected outputs
Domain name and hosting	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management (UWE, FB): ensure the chosen domain and hosting align with the project; Identify a domain name that is brand-appropriate, memorable, and SEO-friendly; verify the availability of the desired domain name and potential alternatives;	name and hosting requirement;	web address;

Infrastructure setup and configuration	DevOps Engineer (SFC): define the technical specifications and standards for the infrastructure; ensure scalability, reliability, and security in the infrastructure design; install, configure, and maintain servers (virtual/shared and physical when needed);	system requirements;	a ready server;
Building and packaging	DevOps Engineer (SFC): build the code to check if its working; package all the files that are ready to be deployed on the server machine;	code; files; database backup;	package to deploy on server;
Testing and deployment	DevOps Engineer (SFC): Deploy the package on the server and test if everything is working.	package;	deployed web platform;
Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management (FB, UWE) in collaboration with the CDD (SFC) and content providers: define the best diss&comm strategies and campaign to ensure high impact in the intended audiences for each of the KERS - this could be done via online events, designated COALESCE Events, or in collaboration with relevant organisations, such as N&R hubs or other stakeholders - COALESCE social media channels, newsletter, etc. Create visual elements such as brochures, images, advertisements, social media graphics, etc.	Timeline of platform releases and product launches	Diss, comm and exploitation strategies
KPIs assessment	CDD team (LUT) - measure number of visits, registered users, downloads (see table 6 for detail)	KPIs table	KPIs report in specific timepoints

	Report to Coordination and Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management team		
--	--	--	--

2.2 Description of iterations and timeline

A co-design and co-development iterations timeline was defined to ensure that CDD activities are timed to coincide with the co-creation of project outputs (tools, services and resources) to be incorporated in the platform, and as possible, key scheduled COALESCE events and/or conferences to better disseminate the platform. Before each public release, two blocks of 6 months period have been outlined (**Table 4**). As an agile process will be used, it may be that the development of some outputs will be faster and others may take longer, depending on their complexity, but it is thought of for internal guidance and better coordination within the consortium activities to predict risks and/or respond to any unforeseen circumstances. CDD outputs and platform releases will align with updated needs, identified resources and audiences as appropriate and may reflect modifications in the proposed timeline.

Table 4. Timeline for iterations – platform development

1st iteration period	2nd iteration period	3rd iteration period	Public releases
M10-15 (January – June 2024)	M16-23 (July–March 2025)	M31-37 (October 2025– March 2026)	M15 (june 2024)
	M24-30 (April – September 2025)	M38-42 (April – September 2026)	M30 (september 2025)
			M42 (september 2026)

2.3 Description of platform releases

The Competence Centre platform and associated tools and SciComm Academy will be released periodically, as one of the major milestones of the COALESCE project, after each block of iterations defined in the previous section. We have predicted three release periods over the course of the COALESCE project, as milestones, occurring once a year (June 2024, September 2025 and September 2026). The following table (**Table 5**) succinctly describes the timeline, outputs, including tools and resources, to be made available within each of the releases. This timeline will be reviewed periodically and may be modified to reflect changes in or additions to the iterations plan.

Table 5. Platform releases, tools and resources for each release and expected dates

Milestone	Milestone title	Outputs (tools and resources)	Due date
MS4	Periodic releases of the platform,	Scicomm innovation cycle; roadmap for rapid mobilisation in times of crisis; criteria of excellence	M15 (June 2024) – 1st release

	including tools and resources	Pedagogical toolkit; library of resources for educators and practitioners; further developments of the crisis navigator tool; ENJOI Observatory; matchmaking tool; process for upload of resources under criteria of excellence; (connection to) interactive tools and/or space for joint events, mutual learning and networking	M30 (September 2025) - 2nd release (initially planned for M33 - December 2025)
		Portfolio of educational services; Impact and self-evaluation tool	M42 (September 2026) - 3rd and final release - initially planned for M37 - March 2027

2.4 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Together with the COALESCE partners and the communication, dissemination and exploitation team, the CDD team will periodically meet to review project KPIs directly related to the platform and integrated tools, services and resources to ensure effectiveness in reaching the intended audiences and achieving the expected outcomes. Key performance indicators for each tool/resource, and related objectives are listed in **Table 6**.

Table 6. Competence Centre and integrated resources KPIs

Objectives	KPI 1	KPI 2	KPI 3
Co-design a self-sustaining CC	1st release platform	2nd release platform	3rd release platform
Transform consolidated knowledge into valuable products	8 tools co-created, including: ENJOI Observatory, interactive tools for networking, matchmaking tool, pedagogical toolkit, scicomm evaluation tool, library of resources, misinformation tool and a scicomm academy	10 resources included with the seal of excellence	-
Encourage capacity building and training and use of resources	Resource library (3.000 online visits); Toolkit (2.000 visits), webpages with available training (3.000 visits), matchmaking tool (+100 users)	-	-

3 Co-design of CC requirements specifications (overall and 1st release)

3.1 Methodology

Prior to defining and implementing the methodology described in section 2.1, to each individual product, we have ignited the ideation process with a thorough analysis of the Description of Action (DoA) for the COALESCE project, a virtual brainstorming session within the CDD team and an internal co-design session with the consortium.

For this first virtual co-design session we used a 5W1H framework in order to broadly identify needs and requirements for the platform, including some of the tools that will be available. It was divided into multiple phases, stakeholder identification and grouping, direct and indirect needs, and matching needs with already planned tools (during the session called “components”), identification of new needs not covered and new tools.

After these, we (re-)defined our initial objectives and deepened into the type of stakeholders and end-users of the platform.

For the next phase, to obtain user expectations, needs and requirements, we addressed multiple stakeholders, focusing on an overall vision of the Competence Centre with five planned tools (including a matchmaking tool, a pedagogical toolkit and a scicomm impact self-evaluation tool. It will include dedicated spaces for the SciComm Academy, a library of resources). We thus conducted a face to face co-design session workshop with end-users – mainly scicomm professionals – as a COALESCE Event – offered as a [pre-event of the Congress on Social Communication of Science \(CCSC 2023\)](#), held in Granada, Spain, under the Spanish Presidency of the EU Council and the EU Year of Skills. In parallel, and in order to facilitate the access and availability to other stakeholders, we have conducted semi-structured interviews to policymakers (including EC, DGs, ERC and EU Parliament, both in-person in Brussels and online) and generalistic and science journalists (online, in-person ENJOI event in Barcelona, on the 14th December 2023).

Thereafter, data was gathered, analysed and discussed with different task leaders – as our “content providers” –, specially those that will be released in the first launch of the virtual platform (i.e. the scicomm innovation cycle, the criteria of excellence and curation process and the scicomm rapid mobilisation roadmap). Together with LUT, user requirements specifications were translated into functional requirements. This process will be continuous throughout the project, having established working periods of 2x6M, for each platform release.

Hereby we detail the sessions co-design methodology.

3.1.1 Co-design sessions for needs and user requirements

For the **first co-design session with the consortium**, held virtually, we used an online board tool (Miro) for an exercise based on the 5W1H framework in order to identify, together with the consortium, the needs and requirements for the platform, including some of the tools that will be available. It was divided into multiple phases, stakeholder identification and grouping, direct and indirect needs, matching needs with already planned tools (during the session called “components”), identification of new needs not covered and new tools.

Duration: 2,5 h, online

Number of attendees: up to 15 + 3 facilitators

Table 7. Co-design session 1 structure.

Duration	Title	Structure
5 min	Participants entry	Participants enter the room. We welcome them and put on some background music.
10 min	Introduction to the topic	We briefly present the objectives of the co-design of the virtual platform for the CC and the session goal: common understanding of the platform.
5 min	Presentation of the session	This dynamic is an adaptation of the 5W1H method: What, Who, Why, Where, When, How. It allows us to set the basis for a common understanding of the platform and for a first conceptualization. Share the Miro board link and explain the basics.
5 min	Initial exercise: Write your name in a post-it	Participants are asked to write their name in a post-it, so that they feel comfortable to use the tool and move around the board.
10 min	Exercise 1 (WHO)	Read stakeholders and add missing ones. Pre-identified stakeholders will already be added to the map before the session starts and we ask to add those not considered.

25 min	Exercise 2 (WHY)	<p>Detect needs for each stakeholder and place them around. The first 5 minutes will be in silence, and the other 20 will be for discussion, grouping of ideas, and building on other people's ideas.</p>
15 min	Exercise 3 (WHAT)	<p>Read the components (i.e tools) and add missing ones/ specify more. The pre-identified components will already be added in the map before the session starts. The first 5 minutes will be in silence, and the other 20 will be for discussion, grouping of ideas, and building on other people's ideas.</p>

20 min	Break	-
25 min	Exercise 4 (HOW.1)	<p>Make the match! Which component(s) will be used to fulfil each need of each stakeholder? Components will need to be copied, not moved from their initial position. If one component fulfils more than one need, it should be copied again.</p>
20 min	Exercise 5 (HOW.2)	<p>Find the gaps – Which needs are not fulfilled by any component? Propose new components to cover those needs. A new set of post-its will be given for this part. This way we will be able to see which components were the last ones to be identified as needed.</p>

		<h2>How (matchmaking)</h2> <p>✎ Make the match! – Match stakeholders and needs with the corresponding components. Copy the components using Ctrl+C, Ctrl+V. Do not delete the components from the "What" area.</p>
5 min	Exercise 6 (HOW.3)	<p>Voting of components – prioritise the components according to those more relevant for most of our stakeholders. The prioritisation will be the starting point to define the landing page. This voting will be done using a functionality of Miro. Each participant will be given 3 votes.</p>
20 min	Landing page (WHERE)	<p>How do you imagine the landing page? – Ideas, references, synergies with other platforms (interoperability). Not a design, but an idea of what they have in mind, how they envision it, and references they may have. A maximum of 5 components will be discussed – the most voted ones.</p>
10 min	Conclusions	Summarise main findings and conclusions.
5 min	Thanks and closing	Next steps.

For the **second co-design session with end-users**, we adapted the 5WIH from co-design session 1 to the face to face format. So, again defining the needs, matchmaking with the tools proposed, evidencing the gaps, and proposing new tools or solutions. Participants were also

encouraged to share best practices and specific examples that can serve as inspiration for the consortium.

Duration: 2h

Number of attendees: up to 30 + 6 facilitators

Profiles of attendees: scicomm professionals and researchers

Table 8. Co-design session 2 structure.

Duration	Title	Script
05 min	Welcome and form groups	Create 4 groups of 6 to 10 people
5 min	Project presentation	Welcome and project presentation
5 min	Session presentation	Brief presentation and session goals SLIDO as ice- breaker with 3 questions
5 min	Introduction to exercise and round of individual presentations	<p>Explain methodology, wooden totem to build a puzzle to obtain our end-goals</p> <p>Each yellow totem will represent a stakeholder group</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers - Scicomm and journalism professionals <p>Round of presentations</p> <p>Note: each phase will have totems with different colours as follows:</p> <p>Yellow: stakeholder group Orange: needs/challenges Blue: tools Red: inspiring examples Green: vote</p>
25 min	Phase needs	<p>Ask participants to propose needs/challenges for each stakeholder group (orange totem).</p> <p>Which are the needs an EU Scicomm CC for scicomm should give response to?</p>
15 min	Break	
20 min	Phase Matchmaking needs	The yellow totems will be removed to fully focus on the tools

	<p>with available tools</p>	<p>and identify the needs they respond to. To do this, all the tabs are organised according to the tools (blue totems)</p> <p>Show on screen tools' descriptions for those available on the totems to facilitate comprehension:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Library - Matchmaking tool - Joint spaces for ML - Scicomm Academy - Impact tool - Mobilisation in times of crisis <p>Now we focus on the tools.</p> <p>What needs do the planned tools respond to?</p> <p>In case some need is not covered by the available tools, new tools can be added so that all needs are covered.</p>
<p>10 min</p>	<p>Phase Inspiration</p>	<p>Introduce references or format ideas which could contribute to the tools (red totem)</p> <p>What format could the tools have? Could you give us any reference</p>

10 min	Prioritise proposals	<p>To finish the exercise, each group has to agree on the priority order for the given tools, with 1 being the most urgent tool to be developed, up to 3. For this, participants have green totems numbered from 1 to 3.</p> <p>Prioritise tools according to relevance and urgency</p>
10 min	Conclusion	Facilitators share main findings and conclusions from each table. Presentation of proposals: each group has 1 minute to share their priority ranking
5 min	Closure	Closure of the session. Thank you to the participants and farewell.

3.1.2 Semi-structured interviews for needs and user requirements

- **Semi-structured interviews to EU-level policymakers** were conducted in order to understand how the Competence Centre can fulfil and align with EU policy agendas, already existing Competence Centres as well as other EU structures in order to predict and plan for collaborations, interoperability concerns and contribute to the sustainability of the Centre.

Moreover, we gathered information of expectations, motivations, needs; we also requested information for benchmarking and asked where policymakers would be willing to contribute to the platform in terms of expertise and resources.

QUESTIONS

1- What are your expectations towards the CC platform, what would motivate you to use it, what would you like to find there (needs)?

2- Is there any particular inspiring resource you would suggest?

3- What would you like to contribute to the platform in terms of expertise and resources?

Number of interviews: 14

Profiles interviewed: Research Managers, Policy Analysts, Investigators, Members of the Parliament, Research and Scicomm Funders at the EU level (institutions they represent: EC, ERC, JRC, EU Parliament)

- **A similar structure was used in the case of science journalists**, although besides personal interviews, an online form was used to gather collective information in the final [local event](#) of the [ENJOI](#) project in the headquarters of SFC was used as an opportunity to gather feedback. Prior to face to face discussion, in order to facilitate the gathering of information, journalists were asked to fill in a questionnaire via a google form, after the event.

QUESTIONS

1- In your role as a journalist what would be your expectations towards the CC platform, what would motivate you to use it, what would you like to find there (needs)?

2- Would any of the planned resources fit your needs? Any further recommendation? Is there any particular inspiring resource you would suggest besides the ones we have planned? (The resources are mentioned on a slide of the presentation: Matchmaking

tool, Rapid Mobilization Tool, Joint Space, SciComm Academy, Impact Assessment Tool, Library of resources)

3- What do you think could be the contribution of a generalist journalist to the platform in terms of expertise and resources?

Number of interviews: 3 (science) + 4 (generalists)

Profiles interviewed: journalist of national scientific magazine (environment), journalist for regional TV channel, board member of regional and national journalists council, general journalist covering also sci & tech news

3.1.3 Technical mapping for functional requirements

After obtaining the initial URS these were then mapped technically in order to deliver a feasible and working solution for these needs. Taking into consideration the virtual platform first release, we focused specifically on the products to be included and overall requirements. The process will be ongoing throughout the project when new tools and contents are produced. The complete process is shown in the diagram below (Figure 2):

Figure 2. Schematic diagram for technical requirements specification gathering.

3.2 Results

3.2.1 Needs and requirements identified for platform and each tool

The first co-design session allowed us to obtain a larger categorization of the stakeholders of the project. We also gathered the needs for each identified stakeholder and organised a list of tools (“components”) for the CC according to the needs, including those already created within the SwafS-19 projects (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Selected area from collaborative map featuring a specific group of connected stakeholders (black – centre), needs (grey – middle), connected tools and possible gaps (light and dark green, respectively – outer side).

Moreover, a thematic mapping was created under 8 themes as shown below.

Identified themes: (science communication *as a*)

- Research & Education
- Profession
- Public Participation
- Policy Making
- Media
- Funding
- Non-governmental
- Ecosystem

❖ Research & Education

[Scicomm professors, researchers, science-communication researchers, living Labs, Universities/RPO leadership, Networks thematic EU projects, Research infrastructures /Institutional Communication Units/ Research evaluation organisms and networks/ Research Networks/ Science publishers (journals and books)]

- Researcher Publisher
- Network
- Institutional
- Educator

❖ Professional

[SciCom Trainers/SciCom professionals / Young Scicomm freelance/ Non traditional Scicommers/ Science Journalists/ Industry]

- Trainer
- Analyst
- Department
- Business
- Scicommer

❖ Public Participation

[Facilitator of citizen participation/Museum Professionals/ Arts Community interested in Science/ Civic centres, libraries / Citizen scientists/ Citizen/ Science sceptics/ Science fans/ Young people]

- Facilitator
- Citizen
- Center

- Community
- Other Professional
- ❖ Policy Making

[Sci/Tech Policy advisors/ Science advisors and Science diplomacy networks/
Policymakers (EU, national, regional, local)/ EC bodies & institutions/Environmental
and other public agency]

- Advisor
- Public Body
- Policy Maker
- ❖ Media

[influencers/Sci/tech related content creator/Press officers of research institutions/
Myth debunkers–fact checking sites/ science journalists/ general journalists]

- Social Media Influencer
- Journalist
- Fact Checker Site
- Press officer
- ❖ Funding

[Science funders (public and private/ Scicomm funders/ Journalism
funders/crowdfunding]

- Funder

Nongovernmental

[NGOs/ Activists]

- NGO
- Activist
- ❖ Ecosystem

[Nature/Ecosystem]

- Nature

Specific needs and requirements were obtained from the co-design sessions with consortium, [end-users](#) (Figure 3) and interviews and have been included in APPENDIX 2 to facilitate reading and were further processed and summarised in section 3.2.2.

Figure 3. Co-design session organised with end-users under the COALESCE Event 2, held in Granada, Spain.

3.2.2 User requirements specifications 1

The results (Appendix 2) were translated into details & requirements for each of the tools and overall virtual platform. It should be noted that during the co-design sessions/interviews not all tools were covered. These were complemented under other tasks' workshops and dedicated meetings between different partners to understand interconnections and provisional structure for content development. The different tools and platform definition and main requirements can be summarised as follows below:

3.2.2.1 Virtual platform

Main purpose:

- Centralised website for the main stakeholders to enable excellent science communication, facilitate access to robust state of the art scientific knowledge and the rapid mobilisation of reliable sources, allow to develop skills and competences related to science communication and journalism

- For scicomm Community: support journalists to find science results in open access; access to curated scicomm resources; replicable methods for impact evaluation
- For citizen or activist: access to useful information for taking citizen or activist actions to increase citizen participation and bottom-up
- For policymakers: Position EU as global leadership in scicomm research and practice

Type of Content:

- An explanation/interpretation of the European scicomm landscape (a COALESCE story)
- Section for inspiration: breaking news? have scicommers/journalists to tell stories based on projects/results
- Access to the rest of the products
- Promotion of a EU Prize for best practices (Reward and recognition of scicomm)

Modalities:

- Multi-language and geographical coverage
- One point for registration

3.2.2.2 Library of resources

Main purpose:

- Find excellent scicomm resources that can be uploaded and classified through a review/curation process.

Type of content:

- Social perception of science
- Introspective section on scientific activity.
- The value of the humanities alongside and on the side of the sciences, and with a necessary interrelation.
- Highlights: curated good practices
 - Code of Best practices- checklist
 - Guide for Inclusive SciComm

- A glossary (to make clear the basic definitions of scicomm terms, e.g. engagement, citizen science)
- Showcase of case-studies
- Latest, most-relevant science-communication findings/research
- Guidebook on how to communicate in times of crisis
- How to perform impact evaluation
- Reports creation tool (Stats about science communication)
- Methods for engaging with the public in open and non-threatening ways
- Promote public interest in science
- Guide for researchers on how to implement scicomm activities in their projects (for example: NEWSERA methodology for 4H-stakeholders engagement)
- Advice on incentives and supporting motivation for scicomm
- Critical takes on scicomm practice
- SciComm Innovation Cycle to tackle challenges on science-society interface
- Evaluation tools
- Access to scientific papers (under embargo)
- Information on topics such as engagement and inclusion
- Tools and methods for addressing misinformation and distrust
- accessible EU-funded results and science policies
- Information on transversal topics, such as GDPR, single market, etc
- Database on traffic in social media and public sphere
- guide for researchers on how to implement scicomm activities in their projects
- Good practices to inspire policy
- Journalists: need to tell a compelling story
- Ethics/ responsible SciComm practices
- Pool of successful initiatives
- Trends in technology and policy
- methods to properly evaluate scientific veracity

- awareness of what science really is

Modalities:

- Search engine
 - by country
 - by keyword
 - By language
 - by topic:
 - Trending/hot topics
 - AI
 - Labor
 - Health
 - Human rights
 - Platform
 - Media
 - Policy
 - Accountability
 - Safety & security
 - Fairness
 - Surveillance & privacy
 - Disinformation & manipulation
 - Open Science
 - RRI
- Visualisation of results
 - Types
 - Publishers
 - Titles
 - Dates of publication
 - Languages

- Automation
- Uploading
 - Review process
 - Validation & Seal of excellence on the documents/contents
 - Publication
 - Correction requested
- Types:
 - Handbooks, audiovisual materials; Image/Sound/Infographic, audiovisual material scientifically validated – creative commons
- Links to other databases
- Interoperability with CORDIS or other
- Link to Science Media Centres

3.2.2.3 Scicomm Academy

Main purpose:

- Provide skills and competences science communication and journalism (based on state of the art and on demand) throughout professionals careers, ensured by a valid certification system for international recognition

Types of Training Modules:

- Train the trainers
- An explanation/interpretation of the EU scicomm landscape (a COALESCE story)
- Mapping of good practices
 - definitions: what is scicomm; competences needed; what is not scicomm; funding available; best practices in short videos; personal experiences
 - Social perception of science
- Case studies–Practices they can look at
- Training in the uses and dangers of AI
- Flaws and Biases of the activity of Science

- Methods to properly evaluate science
- Advice on incentives and supporting motivation for SC
- Advices on strategic communication
 - informal methods/channels and practices like how to use social media or create videos to communicate research
- Training in Competences for Public Science Communication
 - Define the competences of the science communicator
 - Define what is and what is not science communication
 - How does science and the scientific method works
 - Know audiences and adapt content
 - How to avoid rejection
- Training in new channels and social media
- Training for good practices in Journalism
 - Understand Media logics
 - Forbidden sentences when talking to scientists
 - Interview Pills - successful cases - lessons learned
- Management of bias and uncertainty in scicomm
- Training in Public engagement and inclusion
 - Access to studies (also small and local) on the impacts of the public engagement
- Training in methodologies
 - How to co-create? How to develop citizen science

Modalities:

- Training adapted to all scicomm community
- Paid service: Accessible training (low cost option)
 - Low cost training for freelance science writers.
- Many Languages
 - To offer the possibility to upload translation in other languages, not only throughout N&R Hub but via the platform (PlayDecide Model)

- Online and face to face
- Type of content: short videos, infographies, tutorials, podcast, masterclass synchronous online
- Connected to Moodle Platforms

Reward and recognition of scicomm

- Certification for attendance / MOOC Courses with certificates
- Guide for the evaluation of scicomm activities for career assessment (example: CRUE / FECYT in Spain)
- Conduct a study on how scicomm activities in the scientific career are evaluated in different countries and publish a summary – connect with DORA

Network

- Connected to Funding Opportunities- news on PhD and other open positions, competitions, awards, training/courses
- Mentoring programs that guide young journalists in the context of science journalism

3.2.2.4 Impact & Self Assessment Tool

Main purpose:

- To allow impact evaluation of scicomm activities conducted and self evaluation tool, connected to a validation system for recognition

Content:

- Impact Assessment Validated Tools
- Impact pathways evaluation methods

Modality:

- Self-evaluation
- Training modules for self-evaluation (connected with Scicomm Academy)
- Evaluation on demand (perhaps as a self sustaining funding system)

3.2.2.5 Misinformation Tool

Main purpose:

- support journalists, scicomm professionals or other content creator, educators, etc, to screen for resources, methods for tackling misinformation (including prebunking)

Content:

- Dealing with polarisation
- Trust vs misinformation
- How to quickly verify sources
- How to address (and make the most of) AI
- Forward-looking resources: for example, what will be the "next AI"
- Methods such as digital signatures to avoid deep fakes
- a section on the fight against "fake news" or where news review can be requested
- Share successful experiences of fighting against misinformation (for example, health related such as the case of COVID-19)

Modalities:

- AI that helps evaluate the impact of the messages that are created, not only at the level of precision and scientific objectivity, but also from the social commitment to creating non-racist content, using inclusive language, etc
- It is important that this tool assesses issues such as the ideological content included in the news, phantasmagoria, sources, etc.
- Fact Checking tools
- Seal for reliable scientific information
- Multiple languages

3.2.2.6 Matchmaking Tool

Main purpose:

- a "tinder-like" space to connect different stakeholders of interest under a certain scientific topic, or a situation, such as an emergent crisis that needs multiple specialists consultation and mobilisation to allow the best channelling of reliable and trustworthy scientific-based knowledge. It acts in multiple directions, finding the best fit for a scientific source, finding the best fit for a citizen engagement activity, finding the best fit for a scientific news, etc.

Moreover it should allow collaborations to foster trust and build durable relationships between researchers and other stakeholders.

Content:

- Profiles of users: 4H, scicomm professionals, funders, industry, researchers, journalists, citizens, unusual scicomm producers, policymakers
- Profiles of institutions, scientific culture or scicomm units within institutions
- Profiles of professional networks, science academies
- Profiles of projects
- Channels to connect science and policy agendas in Europe (JRC, DG-COM, Agenda from the EU Innovation Council, MPs)
- Channels with policy and decision makers at different governance levels (EU, national, regional, local) to increase recognition and support to the practice
- Explanation of EU science policy landscape
- Share opportunities for short stays between different types of institutions
- ENJOI Observatory
- Face to face activities and networking events (in connection with space for joint events...) - real life tinder

Modalities:

- The platform works also as a “seal”, ensuring that the contacts are reliable.
- Geographical coverage, include user location - city level (to allow meeting in person)
- Multilingual
- System for alert and rapid response
- Open to organised citizens
- Link to social media networks
- Topics (encourage interdisciplinarity)

Current societal issues

Scientific Areas

Policy Agenda

- Availability for consulting services from scicomm professionals in the tool

- Connect with existing diverse and trustworthy sources networks or databases (for example, RED POP, etc), connect with Science Media Centres
- Group and connect similar profiles within themselves (researchers with researchers, scicomm professionals with scicomm professionals..)

3.2.2.7 Mobilisation in time of crisis

Main purpose:

- facilitate the mobilisation of key actors and best scicomm/journalism practices in times of crisis

Content:

- Profiles of key actors
- Spaces for research and practice collaborations
- Learnings from crisis communication
- space available for journalists and scientists to meet and work together to improve the scientific communication produced
- open blog where journalists could share doubts and be able to establish conversations with different experts/professionals for advice.
- Fact files / summaries
- How to communicate in time of crisis and how to properly react in time of crisis that need scientific knowledge – Templates to create visual/audiovisual content in a simple way and that are editable (or communication kits for different specific cases, for example: crisis situation in case of a specific natural disaster)
- Good practices to inspire policy (connected with library of resources)

Modalities:

- Coordination and contact with the major media and journalists, a great emphasis on the humanistic and ethical role of what is happening
- useful and intuitive, accessible from usual channels that were already working before the crisis (telegram, slack, etc.)

3.2.2.8 Space for joint events, ML, and networking

Main purpose:

- a space to allow for the establishment or promotion of joint events, mutual learning between stakeholders and networking

Content:

- Space for specialised media
- Space for related-research areas
- Space for multiple stakeholders
- ENJOI Observatory
- Forum Space (example researchgate) to share concerns, doubts, best practices
- Connection to other channels (tik tok, etc)
- Community of scicommers (discord by topics, channels, slack, telegram, mail)
- Press release services
- Observatory of scicomm trends (updated info on scicomm research methods, processes and results)
- Space for promotion of personal initiatives
- Space for lobby
- Competitions, Funding, Fellowships, Job opportunities

Modalities:

- F2F events - horizontal formats, considering relational aspect
- Navigation map with different centres and events organised

3.2.2.9 Other Tools or considerations

- Advice and resources to obtain evidence in specific cases of malpractice by governments and institutions, as well as support for litigation in cases of serious effects on health or the environment.
- Include a space for National and Regional Hubs (Geographic representation, languages, bottom up, those that are excelling at small scale but with impact)

3.2.3 User requirements specifications 2 – for 1st release

After analysing and reviewing the results in the previous section we organised an interactive informative session to discuss with the consortium/content providers and match current content development with end-users expectations. A common structure of the platform was drafted as shown below (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Competence Centre virtual platform structure draft.

Thereafter, we conducted a second phase for URS-2 specifically oriented to the first release of the platform (Figure 5), which was revealed to be mainly static content.

Figure 5. Competence Centre virtual platform structure draft for first release.

The main structure was defined as being composed of: “About the Competence Centre” (including, Who we are and Where we come from, Mission and Vision and Conceptual Framework – the Scicomm Innovation Cycle), “Scicomm in times of crisis” (later renamed to “Crisis Preparedness” (including a Roadmap for rapid mobilisation and policy briefs)), “Library” (including criteria of excellence and curation process) and “User Registration”.

A specific set of requirements for the first iteration of each of the first main three components (Scicomm Innovation Cycle – within the About section–, Crisis Preparedness and Library) and their conversion into functional requirements is further defined in section 3.2.6.

3.2.4 General high level architecture of the platform

After analysing the initial requirements gathered from both internal and external stakeholders, we have drawn a general high level architecture of what we are trying to achieve. There can be a problem profile looking for a specific solution in the context of science communication. We as a platform will provide a matchmaking feature which can link the problem profile to the solution profile. To reach the right solution, there are both internal and external resources. The internal resources will be the features developed inside the platform whereas there will be resources available from external sources as well.

Figure 6. High level architecture (conceptual diagram).

3.2.5 Functional requirements – virtual platform general

In order to have a more general overview of the functionalities requirements, we have grouped them according to human-oriented, machine-oriented, usability and accessibility, content-based and other categories (Table 9) as shown below. Hereby we can find possible connections with other already existing platforms with complementary competence and skills to science communication such as the ECS (citizen science) or the EOOSC (open science) and others with complementary information (CORDIS, Science Media Centres, etc),

Table 9. Platform overall functionalities

Type	Description
Human oriented	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - matchmaking - mentorship - networking - training - forum - communities of practice (general and by country) - catalogue of individuals, contacts details, projects or areas of expertise - catalogue of associations, networks - recognition (prize) - seal of excellence - how to mobilise in times of crisis
	- good search tool (including an advanced search tool)
	- news, stories and updates
	- calendar of events and trainings
Machine oriented	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interoperability - Connected or linked to other complementary competence and skills platforms (ex. ECS, EOOSC, etc), and EC platforms with complementary resources (CORDIS, DG-Communication, Science Media Centres, etc)
Usability and accessibility requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Easy to use - Dynamic and interactive - Simple - Attractive
Content requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quality: curated list of resources following a criteria and approved by a seal of excellence - Link with already existing resources (for example, those created by the SwafS-19) - Fit to all interested stakeholders (4H, media) -Handbooks -Toolkits -Training -Roadmaps -Guidelines

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -impact evaluation -Resources with different formats for learning -Funding calls - Policy recommendations national and institutional level -contextualised and inclusive (EU level and abroad)
Other suggestions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Languages - multiple both in platform, resources and trainings - guarantee resources quality (seal of excellence) - Inclusivity - personalised user-journeys both regarding stakeholder as well as level of scicomm skills and competences - co-creation: possibility of co-create components of the platform - bottom-up: people should be able to express concerns and experts to support or offer guidance to appropriate experts - allow for multiple levels of engagement: free and paid versions - dedicated curators and/or facilitators and/or moderators (apart from administrator role) - allow certification of training - modularity: whilst building platform - support the visibility of N&R Hubs within the platform, their activities offered, their communities of practice, etc

3.2.6 Functional requirements – for 1st release and beyond

Following the complete process, the final list of technical requirements is drafted to serve as a grey structure and architecture of the intended platform. The initial requirements for the first release of MVP (M15) are based on static content about scicomm innovation cycle, curation tool (criteria of excellence and seal of excellence) and Roadmap and action plan for rapid mobilisation in the times of crisis that will be provided and hosted on the platform, as well as an 'About' page and information in compliance with GDPR. In addition to that, there are some general requirements that are needed for using overall features of the software platform i.e. user registration on the COALESCE platform etc. The finalised list of technical requirements for the MVP (M15) is given in the section below.

The structure of table 10 includes user requirement specification identification number (URS ID) which shows both requirement numbers along with document name. For instance, in "G_1", "G" represents a "general" URS document and "1" represents the requirement code associated with that document. Similarly, other are denoted with their respective Task numbers i.e. T2.1_1 etc. The same column also shows the feature/functionality name in "bold & italic" The second column represents the technical description (TD). The third column represents the "entities", "attributes", "screens", (EAS) and the last column shows the required action (RA).

Table 10. Technical requirements of the virtual platform 1st release.

URS ID	Technical Description (TD)	Entities, Attributes, Screens (EAS)	Required Action (RA)
G_1 T2.2_1 G_2 G_3 User Registration	<p>There are three types of platform users:</p> <p>Public User: Can access resources publicly available on the platform after being published. It has view only rights.</p> <p>Registered User: Is registered with the email. After login, they can access their own or other resources (based on assigned role) and make changes to them. It has view and edit rights (based on assigned role).</p> <p>Master User: Is a registered user who manages the whole platform and assigns roles to other registered Users. It has all the view, edit, and delete rights.</p> <p>There are three types of roles for registered users and each user can have multiple roles:</p> <p>Contributor: This is the first role assigned to every registered user. It can add and view its own resources on the platform. It can only be changed by a Master user.</p> <p>Curator: It can view and edit resources of others. This role can only be assigned by a Maser user.</p> <p>Evaluator: It can view and publish the resource on the platform. This role can only be assigned by a Maser user.</p>	<p>Entities:</p> <p>User User Profile Roles Permission</p> <p>Attributes:</p> <p>Email First Name Last Name Password Role Location</p> <p>Screens:</p> <p>Landing Page (first screen before login with all the top menu buttons)</p> <p>Registration Form (having fields required for registration with mandatory email and confirm password)</p> <p>Login Form (with email and password only along with link for forgot password)</p> <p>Main Page (main screen after login with side menu and top menu)</p> <p>Forget Password Form (email for password reset link)</p> <p>Password Reset Form (with new password and confirm password field)</p> <p>List of Users Page (showing all the registered users in tabular form)</p> <p>User Profile Page (showing details about user profile)</p> <p>Edit User Role Form (for master user to edit role)</p>	<p>LUT</p> <p>Initialise the backend development setup, create database tables and backend functionalities.</p> <p>Communicate the frontend needs and plan your frontend development based on the final screens for incorporating the required look and feel.</p> <p>Provide the logo for the virtual platform.</p> <p>Provide the icons (where required)</p> <p>Provide the overall theme which is required to be used for frontend. This should show the UI/UX of the buttons, files, text fields and other web elements that will be part of the web platform.</p> <p>Provide the final HiFi screens after being reviewed by the concerned leader.</p> <p>The landing page should have a "Quick tab that links pedagogical toolkit with all tools and library of resources"</p> <p>Content Provider Content is required to be displayed on the main landing page showing "Clear understanding on how one can acquire competencies and skills for science communication"</p>

		Edit User Profile Form (for all users to update their profile)	
G_4 T2.2_2, G_8, G_6, G_5 Resource Uploading	<p>A registered user with a contributor role can upload the resource on the platform. The file can be either a link or an actual file. The uploaded resource is then assigned to a user with a curator role. Curator can further assign the resource to the user with the evaluator role.</p> <p>Following two types of resources are uploaded:</p> <p>Link: A medium of any extension is uploaded on some other platform and is linked to this platform.</p> <p>Media: A medium of extensions like (pdf, jpg, mp3, mp4) is uploaded on this platform itself.</p>	<p>Entities: Resource TaskAllocation (relationship table between resource and user to whom it is assigned) Notification</p> <p>Attributes: Title Description Type Uploader ID Upload Date Update Date Language Keywords Category Audience Authors Publisher Year of Publication Licence External Link Approval Status List of Supporting Materials Language</p> <p>Screens: List of Resources Page (showing all the resources uploaded by the user itself with filters on audience and other attributes)</p> <p>Resource Upload Form (screen for providing all the metadata about the resource)</p> <p>Resource Edit Form (screen for editing)</p> <p>Resource Details Page (screen showing all the details of the resource)</p>	<p>LUT Same as above and according to details given in left column</p> <p>Content Provider For multiple language resource support content needs to be translated by the content provider.</p>

		Notification Page (showing all the notifications for the user)	
T2.2_3 Resource Curation	A registered user with evaluator role will be notified about the resource to be evaluated. The resource is evaluated, the criteria of acceptance or rejection is provided by the evaluator.	Entities: Resource Evaluation Results Attributes: Resource ID Remarks Screens: Evaluation Form (where remarks can be added by the evaluator)	LUT Same as above and according to details given in left column Content Provider The notification text
T2.2_4 Resource Publishing	After the evaluation, the resource will be published by the evaluator and the contributor will be notified about the results.	Entities: N/A Attributes: N/A Screens: N/A	LUT Same as above and according to details given in left column Content Provider The notification text
T2.2_5 Resource Presentation	The user with the contributor role can view the results and will not be allowed to modify the content after being published. These rights are only with the curator.	Entities: N/A Attributes: N/A Screens: Seal of Excellence (a graphic that is assigned to only those resources which has seal of excellence) Evaluation Results Screen (page where contributor can see the progress or the final results of resource)	LUT Same as above and according to details given in left column
T2.2_6 User Feedback	If any user makes a comment on the resource, then the curator is notified, and it can be approved or rejected by the curator. Only approved comments will be made public.	Entities: Comment Attributes: Resource ID Comment Text Rating Commented By Approved By Approval Status Screens: Comment Section (a form which can allow	LUT Same as above and according to details given in left column Content Provider The notification text

		commenting on the published resources) Comment Approval Screen (a page where curator can approve the comments)	
T2.2_7 Evaluation Principles	Information page showing the quality criteria AND /evaluation process in text or PDF form.	Entities: N/A Attributes: N/A Screens: Basic content section (page for holding common information for the public users)	LUT Same as above and according to details given in the left column: Content editing. Content Provider The principles of quality evaluation
T2.1 T6.1 General Information	Information pages in the "About" section (includes subpage with scicomm cycle)		Content provider Content related to corresponding section CDD Content editing.
T2.4 Crisis navigator and related content	Information pages in the "Crisis Preparedness" Section (includes subpage with crisis navigator with text and interactive PDF, and subpage with policy briefs, in text, image and link to PDF)		Content provider: Content related to corresponding section CDD Content editing.

3.2.7 Functional requirements – collaboration with ECS and other projects

Collaboration with ECS has started through the signature of a Memorandum of Understanding to collaborate and share knowledge, good practices and challenges of EU-Citizen.Science platform development in connection with COALESCE. In addition, COALESCE partner LUT has been invited to take part of [ECS Platform Working Group](#) at the ECSA for peer learning on their ongoing co-development process to explore potential connections and potential reuse of code, specific contents or structures in terms of new modules and functionalities, reusing resources when possible. One part of both platforms that will be specially looked into to foster connections are the Academies, as both the citizen science community and the science communication community can benefit from the available resources and trainings for their daily work. For subsequent platform releases, the COALESCE team will continue to exchange learnings with their development team under the ECS Platform Working Group of the ECSA.

Finally, mutual learning meetings between COALESCE, ECS, [PATTERN](#), and the [REINFORCING](#) projects are taking place in order to define complementary actions for platform usability, services development, dissemination and exploitation.

4 Risks

Following the Project Management Handbook, we hereby describe and complement risks identified concerning the CDD strategy and associated risk-mitigation measures, as indicated in the table below (Table 11).

Table 11. Associated risks and mitigation strategies.

Risk identified	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Delays in meeting milestones or deliverables	Continuous monitoring of the project performance. If required, reallocation of resources, tasks and responsibilities
Quality of product development with software and functional requirements of platform	One to one meeting between partner responsible and coordinator for the review of timing and quality of product development in line with effective functional requirements for platform release
Ethics issues related to protection of data and privacy	A Data Management Plan and Ethics deliverable will develop solutions to handle the potential misuse of research results, personal data and confidentiality
Technical problems detected by users	Technical support email inserted in the platform - techsupport@scicommcentre.eu

5 Final Remarks

This report documents the co-design-co-development methodological framework to be used under the COALESCE project. As described flexibility and agility will be fundamental in order to guarantee efficiency but at the same time respecting high quality standards. Initial requirements have been gathered for the Competence Centre first release and will be continuously updated throughout the project in several iteration cycles, digested from co-creation and participatory exercises, used as gold standard. At the same time as meetings with the ECS project and others will be periodically used to exchange learnings between development teams, such as the Platforms Working Group of the ECSA, or cross-projects meetings between ECS-COALESCE-PATTERN-REINFORCING or Skills4EOSC to understand collaborations for future versions of platforms in terms of new modules and functionalities, reusing resources when possible and planning for complementarities.

6 Acknowledgements

The COALESCE consortium acknowledges all the representatives of the quadruple helix (citizens, researchers, policymakers and industry), science communication professionals and journalists, and members of the COALESCE community of practice, that were involved in the interviews and workshops for their generous contributions.

7 Project details

COALESCE Coordinated Opportunities for Advanced Leadership and Engagement in Science Communication in Europe

PARTNERS

Project website <https://coalesceproject.eu>

Competence Centre website <https://scicommcentre.eu>

For more information please contact: info@coalesceproject.eu

Join our Community of Practice:

Appendix 1

User Requirements Specification (URS)

State of the art to start 1st iteration	
Date	
Name of feature	Feature is a tool, a service, component that should be included in the platform
Main goal	<p>This should give a brief overview of what is to be created, in non-technical terms. It should be written in a narrative or descriptive style (ie not a checklist or abbreviated language), and outline what the product is intended to do. To assist with writing this section, ask the following questions:</p> <p>Definition: What am I trying to achieve? The ... is a ...</p> <p>Purpose: What problems will this product solve? The ... will help to...</p> <p>How will it streamline or improve the existing system, or similar product in the marketplace (if one exists)?</p> <p>Products internal connection: please indicate if this product should be connected to other products of the platform. Which ones?</p>
Visual idea	Include any sketch available
Structure	<p>Based on your own findings and stakeholders needs and expectations, please list the information on the following categories:</p> <p>Main definition: Content: Modalities:</p>
Type of users and roles envisioned	<p>Examples:</p> <p>contributor a person who publishes content, such as resources explorer a person who looks for relevant information or contacts curator ... administrator a person with administrator privileges etc</p>
Related Task(s)	Indicate the main task which will create this component, its current stage and planned forthcoming actions
Working Months (Mx)	<p>Mx-Mx Please indicate multiple stages and expected outputs to be developed</p>
Expected 1st release date in platform	Mx

How do you expect it to be in its first release?	Interactive/static, etc..
Team (names, contacts)	
Reviewed by / date	
Meeting	
Feedback from meeting	Summary
To do	
Components/milestones/dates	

Details user requirements specifications (digest from co-design session)						
Code (#)	User's input (requirement, user story, etc)	Description	Relevance (low, medium, high or very high)	Decision	Status	Technical Requirement Mapping
No.	example: welcome screen	example: As an administrator, I'd like the welcome screen to include a link to the user's profile, as well as links to uploaded documents by the user.	Very... ▾	T... ▾	N... ▾	
No.			Very... ▾	T... ▾	N... ▾	
No.			Very... ▾	T... ▾	N... ▾	

Appendix 2

The results obtained from the co-design sessions and semi-structured interviews have been classified and are presented in a table format for each the tool/product/service according to:

- Needs identified
- Type of stakeholder reporting
- Correlated need
- Benchmarking or comments on core functionalities

A2.1 Virtual platform

Stakeholder reporting (I am a..)	Needs identified (and I want to..)	Correlated need	Benchmarking (References or comments)
Polymakers	have access to scicomm resources and information in multi-languages and reflecting local contexts (EU level)		
Polymakers	support journalists to find science results in open access		
Science & Generalist Journalist	Have access to useful information for taking citizen or activist actions	Advice and resources to obtain evidence in specific cases of malpractice by governments and institutions, as well as support for litigation in cases of serious effects on health or the environment.	https://project.scishops.eu/
Polymakers	that In-depth relationships between researchers and journalists are promoted via the platform		
Polymakers	Have access to learnings from what is already available		Interoperability with CORDIS
Polymakers	rapidly mobilise agents and resources in a crisis		Interoperability with EDMO and other Competence Centres
Science & Generalist Journalist	access to information related to scicomm		A communication campaign with advertising investment is necessary to publicise all services once they are available to professionals and citizens.
Researchers	have scicommers/journalists to tell stories based on their projects/results		A dedicated section for inspiration (not "tool")

Policy makers	connect researchers with current policy agenda and/or transversal topics		
Policy makers	The platform to position itself as reference hub in scicomm globally	An explanation/interpretation of the EU scicomm landscape (a COALESCE story)	
Policy makers	Increase citizen participation and bottom-up		
Policy makers	Have a dedicated space to the national and regional hubs	Content adapted to local contexts and languages	
Policy makers	Promote reward and recognition of scicomm	Policy briefs; coalesce events; seal of excellence	
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Apply for a EU Prize for best practices	Highlights: curated good practices	Recognition News on phd and other open positions, competitions, awards, training/courses...
Scicomm professionals	Have access to a centralised platform for scicomm		https://comunicacioncientifica.fecyt.es/ – local site, share scicomm resources, analysis of the local/current state of scicomm, blogs on scicomm topics, a scicomm researchers database and events and training on scicomm
Scicomm professionals	Have access to a centralised platform for scicomm		Australian website that has a more needs-based approach: https://www.clips.edu.au/
journalists	Have an open access system for international press review? Or with a lower cost than subscribing to many international media.		COALESCE might ask the collaboration / support of important international media which will offer some content to journalists who will subscribe to a cheap COALESCE service of press review (i.e. COALESCE does not pay the media, or to some limited extent, and journalists subscribe the service to COALESCE as part of a sustainability programme).

A2.2 Library of resources

Stakeholder reporting	Needs identified	Correlated need	Benchmarking (References or comments)
Researchers	communication in times of crisis; audiovisual materials; links to other databases impact evaluation		
Researchers	Resources toolkit		https://questproject.eu/toolkits/
Researchers	good database of resources		https://www.informalscience.org/
Policymaker	good database of resources		https://sciencemediacentre.es/en - example on how to organise the library resources according to the user (journalists, scientists, press offices, etc)
	database of reliable data sources, i.e. online sources of (open) data available to journalists.		The database should be navigable by keywords.
Researchers	Curated scicomm material		https://playdecide.eu/ An example of a website in which you can download materials, templates, translate materials and submit them again in the web (with a referee process)
Researchers	Social perception of science	Highlights: curated good practices	Handbooks
Researchers	easy scicomm materials with best practices to replicate	Highlights: curated good practices	
Researchers	Methods for engaging with the public in open and non-threatening ways		guide for researchers on how to implement scicomm activities in their projects NEWSERA methodology for 4H stakeholders engagement
Researchers	(self-) evaluation tools	Advice on incentives and supporting motivation for scicomm	

Researchers	Advice on incentives and supporting motivation for SC	(self-) evaluation tools	
Researchers	Critical takes on scicomm practice	Highlights: curated good practices SciComm Innovation Cycle to tackle challenges on science-society interface	Discussion space- Worst practices?
Scicomm professionals - practitioners	Social perception of science	Handbooks	
Scicomm professionals - practitioners	Sharing of good practices	Highlights: curated good practices	
Scicomm professionals - practitioners	Evaluation tools	Training modules	
Scicomm professionals - practitioners	Find materials (tools, information) useful for them		
Scicomm professionals - practitioners	Promote public interest in science	report on science perception	
Scicomm professionals - practitioners	lack of Code of Best practices	checklist	
Scicomm professionals - practitioners	Access to scientific papers under embargo		EUREKALERT
Scicomm professionals - practitioners	Image/Sound/Infographic Library CC		Website CÁTEDRA DE DIVULGACIÓN CIENTÍFICA del P. VASCO
Scicomm professionals - practitioners	audiovisual material scientifically validated - creative commons		Search engine - country - key word - language - type of material
Scicomm professionals - Researcher	Information on engagement, inclusion		FECYT Guide for Inclusive SciComm
Scicomm professionals - Researcher	Database on traffic in social media and public sphere	Apps, Gamification	

Policy makers	Tools and methods for addressing misinformation and distrust.	Scicomm Academy	
Policy makers	A glossary (to make clear the basic definitions of SC terms, e.g. engagement, citizen science)		
Policy makers	guide for researchers on how to implement scicomm activities in their projects		
Policy makers	Ethics/ responsible SciComm practice		
Policy makers	Pool of successful initiatives		
Policy makers	guide for researchers on how to implement scicomm activities in their projects	A separate section for inspiration (not "tool")	
Policy makers	Good practices to inspire policy	Mobilisation in crisis	A dedicated section for inspiration (not "tool")
Journalists	Journalists: need to tell a compelling story		A dedicated section for inspiration (not "tool")
Journalists	methods to properly evaluate science	Handbooks Impact and self evaluation tool Training modules	
Journalists	Trends in technology and policy	An explanation/int erpretation of the European scicomm landscape (a COALESCE story)	
Journalists	reliable basic information on main "trending" scientific topics (e.g. dark matter, climate, etc.), that journalists can refer to and use to learn more on those topics;		

Journalists	Showcase of best case examples	Highlights: curated good practices	Examples of best practices from different countries, to be able to compare work and methods with colleagues.
Policymakers	Information on transversal topics, such as GDPR, single market, etc	Connect with RRI platform, etc	
Policymakers	accessible EU-funded results and science policies	CORDIS, Horizon Open (CORDIS can be a driven force for the platform - allies and partners)	
Researchers	Latest, most-relevant science-communication findings/research	An explanation/int interpretation of the European scicomm landscape (a COALESCE story)	
Science & Generalist Journalist	awareness of what science really is	Introspective section on scientific activity. A serious reflection on what science is (but really serious, not the nonsense and false simplifications of high school and its supposed "scientific method"), a section with the events and activities of each region, a section for a humanistic committee	claim the value of the humanities alongside and on the side of the sciences, and with a necessary interrelation. Scientific dissemination is always accompanied by philosophical "assumptions" that must be carefully studied and considered. I think a humanistic committee should include this dimension. In addition to assuming that the ideology of technical-scientific progress is an unwanted companion when science is disseminated.

A.2.3 Scicomm Academy

Stakeholder reporting	Needs identified	Correlated need	Benchmarking (References or comments)
Researchers	(self-)evaluation tools	Advice on incentives and supporting motivation for SC	
Researchers	Advice on incentives and supporting motivation for SC	(self-)evaluation tools	
Researchers	Advice on strategic communication		
Researchers	Train the trainers modules		
Researchers	recognition and/or certification	Highlights: curated good practices	The seal of excellence is meant for resources. What about a certificate for people who attend our activities, etc?
Researchers	informal methods/channels and practices like how to use social media or create videos to communicate research	Highlights: curated good practices	
Researchers	Practices they can look at as case studies	Highlights: curated good practices	
Researchers	recognition and/or certification	Highlights: curated good practices	The seal of excellence is meant for resources. What about a certificate for people who attend activities, etc?
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Funding opportunities	News on phd and other open positions, competitions, awards, training/courses...	
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	accessible training – cost may be a barrier for some	Training modules	

Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Evaluation tools	Library of Resources	
scicomm professionals – practitioners	training (in own language)		connection with moodle
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Define the competences of the science communicator	Training in competences for public science communication	MOOC Courses with certificates
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Lack of specialisation	Training adapted to scicomm professionals, journalists	
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Training good practices in journalism (for researchers)		Short videos, infographies, tutorials, podcast
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Define what is and what is not science communication		
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	How does science and the scientific method works		
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Know audiences and adapt content		Seminars, workshops face to face
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Forbidden sentences when talking to scientists		EXPERT COURSE U . OVIEDO IU.VALENCIA
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Training in engagement, inclusion, direct participation		Interview Pills – successful cases – lessons learned
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Training in new channels and social media (TIK TOK , CR)	masterclass synchronous online	PLATZI
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Understand Media logic and ecosystem		
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Management of bias and uncertainty in scicomm		

Scicomm professionals – practitioners	lack of specialisation of a service to verify news and access to sources;		
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	directed to different audiences		
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	how to avoid rejection		
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	new channels for scicomm		
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	good practices for journalism		
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	how to lead with uncertainty podcast, videos, etc		
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	definitions: what is scicomm; competences needed; what is not scicomm; funding available; best practices in short videos; personal experiences		
Researchers	EU Prize for best practices	Open call for the Prize	
Scicomm professionals – Researchers	Training	Tutorials, Courses	Decalogue PCST
Scicomm professionals – Researchers	Mapping of good practices		
Scicomm professionals – Researchers	Training in methodologies		Sparks ToolKit Ecsite
Scicomm professionals – Researchers	How to co-create? How to develop citizen science?		Sparks ToolKit Ecsite

Policymakers	Access to studies (also small and local) on the impacts of the public engagement	Reports creation tool (Stats about science communication)	Social perception of science An explanation/interpretation of the European scicomm landscape (a COALESCE story)
Science & General Journalist	mentoring programs that guide young journalists in the context of science journalism		The possibility of being able to talk to someone who already has a consolidated career can help young journalists guidance, discover new training or job opportunities.
Science & General Journalist	training		It should include short and simple courses for professional retraining (capacity building).
Science & General Journalist			Training in the uses and dangers of AI is important
Science & General Journalist			courses that consider the activity of science with its flaws and biases
Science & General Journalist			Possibility of online and in-person training. It would also be very good if face-to-face training were done in different centres to make it easier for professionals to access these courses in different parts of Europe.
Science & General Journalist	forbidden sentences you should not say when you (as a journalist) talk with a scientist		
Media	AI is a particularly hot topic for journalists. Training that is relevant		Topic focus
Media	Low cost training for freelance science writers. Many need to upskill at their own cost (also time not just monetary cost)		
Media	Materials in a variety of languages	ENJOI Observatory	To offer the possibility to upload translation in other languages, Not only throughout N&R Hub but via the platform (PlayDecide model)

Media	sources of data and useful publications		The library of resources and references can answer to that need only if updated very frequently (or fed by people bottom up and the referee process is quick). Different topics/areas? i.e. a good indexing
	How to deal with uncertainty / Misinformation	Misinformation tool Training modules	
	methods to properly evaluate science	Handbooks Impact and self evaluation tool Library of resources	
	Train the trainers		
	Trainings, summer schools, resources for researchers to reach different audiences		

A.2.4 Matchmaking Tool

Stakeholder reporting	Needs identified	Correlated need	Benchmarking (References or comments)
Researchers	Channels to connect with communicators, funders, industry, other researchers		
Researchers	Identify other institutions to apply for funding	News on phd and other open positions, competitions, awards, training/courses	An explanation/interpretation of the European scicomm landscape (a COALESCE story)
Researchers	Increase connection /channels with researchers		
Researchers	Contacts with "unusual" scicomm producers		
Researchers	Research and practice collaborations	Rapid mobilisation roadmap	
Researchers	ways to engage with related research areas	Space for joint events, ML and networking	
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	networking with other scicommers and scientists	ENJOI Observatory	The golden age of the SciComm community on Twitter is over – could this be an opportunity? Discussion space
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Know researchers research and research centres	Make it real – short stays between different types of institutions	
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Networking between scicommers and researchers	Make it real – short stays between different types of institutions	
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Link with university Units of Scientific Culture	Make it real – short stays between	

		different types of institutions	
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Updated network of scicommers in social media	Make it real – short stays between different types of institutions	
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Access to truthful and diverse sources		RED POP; portal Iberoamericano FECYT; FUNDACIÓN DESCUBRE ANDALUCÍA
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	consulting to projects		
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	need for connection with scicommers themselves		
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	common networks within researchers, journalists, or others		
Policy makers	foster trust in science and build trust between researchers and other stakeholders		
Policy makers	journalists to connect with key scientists in particular areas; and science projects		App – Filters by Interest. (Aesthetics is important)
Policy makers	Connection of 4H stakeholders with policy makers		
Policy makers	bring science academies together		
Policy makers	Contacts of trustworthy scientists to refer to according to the topic of expertise		
Policy makers	Channels to connect science and policy	An explanation/interpretation of the European scicomm landscape (a COALESCE story)	

Science & General Journalist	space available for journalists and scientists to meet and work together to improve the scientific communication produced	open blog where journalists could share our doubts and be able to establish conversations with different professionals who would advise us in the best possible way.	Perhaps several expert and experienced people could be appointed to answer users' questions and thus try to respond to their concerns. example: https://forum.meetoptics.com/t/inke-d-vs-non-inked-lenses/51
Science & General Journalist	connection with multiple stakeholders		open to organised citizens
Science & General Journalist			considers enough agents, and encourages interdisciplinarity.
Science & General Journalist			possibility of meeting the scientist in question in person - include the users' location (not exact, but the city at least)
Journalists	source of experts in different countries		
Journalists	Fact files / summaries		
Journalists	Journalists: super-fast turnaround	Rapid mobilisation roadmap	
Polymakers	connect researchers with the policy agenda	DG-COM, JRC, Agenda from the EIC (European Innovation Council)	
Scicomm professionals - practitioners	Connection with policy and decision makers at different governance levels (EU, national, regional, local) to increase recognition and support to the practice	An explanation/interpretation of the European scicomm landscape (a COALESCE story)	

A.2.5 Rapid mobilisation in times of crisis

Stakeholder reporting	Needs identified	Correlated need	Benchmarking (References or comments)
Researchers	Research and practice collaborations	Matchmaking tool	
Policymakers	Consider learnings from crisis communication		
Policymakers	rapid mobilisation of key actors How to communicate in time of crisis and how to properly react in time of crisis that needs scientific knowledge	Science Media Centres	
Science & General Journalist			Templates to create visual/audiovisual content in a simple way and that are editable (or communication kits for different specific cases, for example: crisis situation in case of a specific natural disaster)
Science & General Journalist			Coordination and contact with the major media and journalists, a great emphasis on the humanistic and ethical role of what is happening
Science & General Journalist			It must be useful and intuitive, accessible from usual channels that were already working before the crisis (telegram, slack, etc.
Journalists	reliable contacts, that could be contacted for interviews or any other need.	Matchmaking tool	The platform works also as a "seal", ensuring that the contacts are reliable.
Policymakers	Good practices to inspire policy	Handbooks	A separate section for inspiration (not "tool")
Journalists	Journalists: super-fast turnaround	Matchmaking tool	rapid mobilisation of sources

A.2.6 Space for joint events, ML, and networking

Stakeholder reporting	Needs identified	Correlated need	Benchmarking (References or comments)
Researchers	ways to engage with related research areas	Matchmaking tool	
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Connect with other professionals, scientists and policy makers	Matchmaking tool	
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Space for specialised media		ENJOI Observatory
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Shared channels (eg. TIK TOK)		
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Create a community of scicommers (they are not connected now))	DISCORD by topics, channels, SLACK, TELEGRAM, mail, BASECAMP (CLOSED)	
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Science Communication Funding Opportunities		
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Press release services		
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Access to updated information about scientific research processes and results	Observatory of scicomm trends	
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Promotion of personal initiatives		
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Real life Tinder	Matchmaking Tool	
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	spaces for lobby, competitions – individual people could access		

Scicomm professionals – Researchers	Forum Space: Meetings between researchers and professionals	F2F events	Horizontal Formats, consider Relational Aspect
Science & General Journalist	a place to share concerns and doubts with other scicomm professionals (whether they are popularizers, journalists or communicators)		Researchgate forum
Science & General Journalist	Sharing examples of best practices.		Sharing knowledge with other colleagues through an online tool (e.g., forum)
Science & General Journalist	find new job opportunities, both national and international, private and public.	job board to find out about new job opportunities (international, national, public, private, scholarships, etc.).	Young science journalists need support networks to help them build their careers and feel "that they belong." With the latter, what I mean is that being halfway between journalism and science means not being part of any group. Creating this sense of belonging through the centre, I believe, would be of great help in inspiring us to work for excellence in scicomm.
Science & General Journalist	networking	Navigation map with the different centres and events that are organised	

A.2.7 Impact & Self Assessment Tool

Stakeholder reporting	Needs identified	Correlated need	Benchmarking (References or comments)
Scicomm professionals – Researchers	Lack of Recognition	Validation System for recognition	Guide SciComm Evaluation CRUE / FECYT
Scicomm professionals – Researchers	Validated tools for evaluation	Evaluation of all countries and publish a summary	
Researchers	Self-evaluation tools		
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Self-evaluation tools	Training modules	
Policymakers	Evaluation tools		
Science & General Journalist			Transparent in the form of evaluation, allow evaluation on demand (perhaps as a financing system)

A.2.8 Misinformation Tool

Stakeholder reporting	Needs identified	Correlated need	Benchmarking (References or comments)
Polymakers	Dealing with polarisation		
Polymakers	Trust vs misinformation	Rapid mobilisation roadmap	
Polymakers	How to address (and make the most of) AI	Scicomm Academy; Rapid mobilisation roadmap	Short updating seminars Discussion space? Forward-looking resources: what will be the "next AI"
Polymakers	SciComm Innovation Cycle to tackle challenges on science-society interface		
	awareness of what science really is	a section on the fight against "fake news" or where news review can be requested	Learn from successful experiences
Polymakers	Reliable scientific information	Seal of excellence	Health related examples? Fact checking Multiple Languages Digital signatures to avoid deep fakes
Science & General Journalist			AI that helps evaluate the impact of the messages that are created, not only at the level of precision and scientific objectivity, but also from the social commitment to creating non-racist content, using inclusive language, etc.
Science & General Journalist			It is important that this tool assesses issues such as the ideological content included in the news, phantasmagoria, sources, etc.

A.2.9 Other tools

Some other ideas of tools came up along the process and are listed in the following table.

Stakeholder reporting	Needs identified	Correlated need	Benchmarking (References or comments)
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Lobby with Funding Agencies	Lobby office	
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Lobby with Funding Agencies	Science Observatory	
Scicomm professionals – practitioners		Consulting for career development for independent professionals	
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	citizen participation	Gamification to motivate citizen participation	
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	Know what interests society	Virtual and physical surveys to disseminate and obtain useful information	Totems to promote surveys – share results
Scicomm professionals – practitioners	support on reaching audiences	Area for external consulting of projects	
Science & Generalist Journalist		A committee of humanistic influence that can be consulted about the adequacy of forms and contents when carrying out science communication: especially if it is rapid or emergency communication.	https://www.wearedavinci.com/
Science & Generalist Journalist		A section that ensures the	It is not at all positive that scientific news is considered

		inclusion or promotion of critical thinking in the communication capsules.	dogmatically and that should also be at the centre.
Researchers	Updated scicomm contents built bottom-up	Reports creation tool (stats about science communication)	A collaborative collection of data under the same topic with the same methods? ROSE project grouping data (provided by science) and then grouping opinions (provided by the society)
Science & Generalist Journalist	international testing panel with invited professionals, who will give feedback to materials and services. necessity to have a referee panel, but this idea involves general journalists, i.e. not particularly expert audiences, and not for the seal of excellence but for any kind of service.		